
Effect of Commitment, Motivation and Feedback to Job Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of variable commitment, motivation and feedback on Job Performance at PT BPR ADB and PT. BPR EUJ. Samples to be taken in this study of 100% of the target population. Data were collected using the questionnaire method by providing a list of questions or questionnaires directly to the respondents. Techniques of data analysis in this study using the data validity test with validity and reliability, multiple linear regression analysis, the classical assumption test, F test, t test, analysis of the coefficient of multiple determination and analysis of the partial coefficient of determination. The results showed that BPR. ADB, variable commitment, motivation and feedback simultaneously significant effect on Job Performance variables. The independent variables are: commitment to partially significant effect on Job Performance. Meanwhile, two other independent variables are: the motivation and the feedback effect is not significant to the performance. Commitment is an independent variable that has the most impact on performance. BPR. EUJ, variable commitment, motivation and feedback simultaneously significantly effect on Job Performance variables. The independent variables are motivation partially significant effect on Job Performance. Meanwhile, the two other independent variables are: commitment and the feedback effect is not significant to the performance. Motivation is an independent variable that has the most impact on performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Competition in the global market can be won if companies always provide superior service to consumers, develop new capabilities and commitments to quality, develop innovation, creativity, initiative and manage human

resources more effectively (Walker, 2002:1). Effective management of human resources can increase the commitment of human resources to quality. Without employee commitment to quality, quality improvement efforts will not succeed. An important thing that employee commitment to quality is the leadership

commitment to quality. To tika employees accept the fact that the management has a commitment to quality, they tend to be more committed to the quality (Howard & Foster 2004:5).

Commitment is a strong belief in and support of the values and goals to be achieved (Mowday et al, 1979; Darma, 2004). According Simanjuntak (2005:1), the commitment is the ability to take responsibility for things that are entrusted to a person. The commitment has nothing to do at all with talent, intelligence or talent. With a strong commitment will enable a person to spend additional physical, mental and spiritual resources that can be obtained, otherwise without commitment the big jobs will be difficult to do. According to Steers and Porter (2003:520), a form of work commitment that arises not only passive loyalty, but also involves an active relationship with the work organization that has the aim of giving all efforts for the success of the work organization concerned.

Motivation is a demand or drive for the fulfillment of individual needs and demands or encouragement that comes from the environment, then implemented in the form of behavior. According to Manahan (2004), motivation is a mental drive towards individuals or people as group members in responding to an event in society. Jewel and Marc (1998), motivation refers to the amount of power that generates, directs and sustains effort in certain behaviors.

The process feeds through a process of evaluation for the development of individuals, usually the manager. In this system (Antonioni, 1996), individuals evaluate themselves and receive feedback from other organizational members. Feedback is coming from the boss directly and co-work (*peer*), and from subordinates if the individual is a manager. Even that feedback can come from customers. This system has emerged as an important performance appraisal tool in recent years and, more importantly as a human resource development tool. By comparing the results of one's own evaluation and those of others, we can see gaps that can provide useful information for personnel development goals.

According to Hasibuan (2002) Job Performance is a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him, which are based on skill, experience, and

sincerity. According to Martoyo (2000) factors that can affect employee performance or employee productivity, including motivation, job satisfaction, stress levels, physical conditions of work, compensation systems for economic aspects, technical aspects, and other behaviors. If employee performance is not getting enough attention, it can result in things that are not desirable, such as the results of work that is not optimal. For this reason, company leaders must really pay attention to organizational commitment factors that affect Job Performance.

Devi (2009) examined the variables of job satisfaction and motivation on employee performance with commitment as an *intervening* variable. The results of the study the results showed that the variable of job satisfaction had a significant positive effect on commitment, but the motivation variable showed no significant positive effect on commitment. Furthermore, the variables of job satisfaction and motivation show a significant positive effect on employee Job Performance. On the other hand, the relationship between commitments is not significantly positive on employee Job Performance. Research Empirical who else is done by Ariyani (2001). Researchers used training variables, incentives and feedback on motivation and Job Performance, and suggested that training, incentives and feedback had a positive effect on motivation and motivation had a positive effect on Job Performance.

This study was carried out specifically to determine the effect of commitment, motivation and feedback variables on Job Performance. Researchers are interested in replicating research conducted by Ariyani (2001) with the same model, in order to see the consistency of the research results obtained. In this study, the training variables and incentives contained in Ariyani's (2001) research were replaced by the commitment and motivation variables. The equation of this study with the research conducted by Ariyani (2001) lies in the use of Job Performance variables as the dependent variable. Differences of this research with the research conducted by Ariyani (2001) in addition located on respondents who becomes the object of research, there is also the independent variable.

This research was conducted at BPR ADB and BPR EUJ. The researcher took the object of research at BPR ADB and BPR EUJ

because researchers discovered a different phenomenon. BPR ADB is currently experiencing liquidity problems, where many bad loans occur. Whereas at BPR EUJ, researchers found that the BPR experienced a rapid development amid very tight competition where many micro banks were established by state-owned banks and national private banks.

In this regard, researchers are trying to relate the phenomenon that occurs in BPR ADB and BPR EUJ with employee Job Performance. Researchers are interested in examining how the Commitment, Motivation and Feedback that occur at BPR ADB and BPR EUJ. Based on the background above, the issues that will be discussed in this study are, is there an influence between the variables of commitment, motivation and feedback on Job Performance at PT. BPR ADB and PT. BPR EUJ?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Suprihanto, et al (2003:52-53) states that the theory of the determination of the destination (*goal-setting theory*) is a theory which states that the objectives of the nature of specific or hard tend to generate performance (*performance*) higher. Achieving goals is done through participatory efforts. Even so many people do not necessarily do the achievement of goals. In achieving the goal that is participatory has a positive impact in the form of the emergence of acceptance (*acceptance*), meaning that as difficult as anything if the person has been receiving a job then it will run well. While it is, the achievement of objectives that participatory can also have a negative impact, namely the emergence of superiority in those who have a higher capacity.

Locke's Goal Setting Theory says that individual goals and intentions that are realized are the main determinants of behavior. People's behavior will continue until the behavior reaches a higher level of achievement.

According to this theory, achievement will depend on the level of difficulty of the goal, the detail of the goal, and one's commitment to the goal. Objectives are harder will make people frustrated that his performance are also low. Destination of detail will affect the understanding of a person to the destination where one is more aware of and understand the purpose will be accomplished better.

Performance appraisal is very important for an organization. With the performance evaluation, an organization can see to what extent human factors can support the goals of an organization. Assessment of the achievement can motivate employees to be motivated to work much better. By because it is necessary to assess the proper and consistent achievement.

Performance appraisal is a formal process to periodically review and evaluate one's Job Performance. This achievement evaluation process is intended to understand one's Job Performance, where this activity consists of identification, observation, measurement and development of employee work in an organization (Panggabean:2002).

This study refers to the results of previous studies conducted by Ariyani (2001) who examined the effect of training perceptions, incentives and feedback on motivation and Job Performance. This study aimed to determine the effect of job training, incentives and feedback on employee motivation levels. The analytical method used is multiple linear regression analysis.

Aside from referring to Ariyani's research, this study also refers to research by Devi (2009), with a sample of 50 respondents. This research is aimed at analyzing the effect of job satisfaction, motivation and commitment on employee Job Performance. The analytical method used is multiple linear regression analysis.

Commitment and Impact on Job Performance

Mabley et. al (1979) in Suwandi and Nur Indriantoro (1999) defines organizational commitment as the frequency of identification frequency and the level of attachment to the belief in trying the best for the organization and the existence of a definite desire to maintain participation in the organization. Robbins (2003) states that commitment is one of the attitudes that reflects feelings of like or dislike for the organization at work. Meyer and Allen (1993) put forward three components about commitment:

- 1). *Affective Commitment*, occurs when employees want to be part of an organization because of *emotional attachments* or feel they have the same values as the organization, 2). *Continuance Commitment*, i.e. the willingness of individuals to stay afloat in organizations

because they do not find other jobs or because certain economic rewards 3). *Normative Commitment* arises from employee values. Employees remain members of the organization because there is an awareness that commitment to the organization is the right thing to do.

Commitment is the ability to take responsibility for things entrusted to someone. With a strong commitment will enable a person to spend additional physical, mental and spiritual resources that can be obtained, otherwise without commitment the big work will be difficult to do. According to Steers and Porter (2003:520), a form of work commitment that arises not only is passive loyalty, but also involves an active relationship with work organizations that have the goal of giving all efforts for the success of the work organization concerned.

In Devi's study (2009), one of the independent variables is commitment. The results of his research indicate that partially commitment has a significant effect on employee Job Performance. Because commitment shows an employee's strong belief in the values and goals to be achieved in the organization, so employees who have high commitment will always have a high view and loyalty also always prioritize the interests of the company or organization. It will naturally bring employee commitment to the organization and will improve Job Performance. Therefore, the formulation of the proposed hypothesis is:

H1 : commitment influences Job Performance

Motivation and Effect on Job Performance

Motivation is an expertise in directing employees to organizational goals so they want to work and try so that the desires of employees and organizational goals can be achieved. Someone's motivation to do a job because of a life need that must be met. This need can be in the form of economic needs, namely to obtain money, while non-economic needs can be interpreted as the need to obtain more advanced awards and desires. With all these needs, a person is required to be more active and active in working, to achieve this it requires motivation in doing work, because it can encourage someone to work and always want to continue their business. Therefore, if an employee who is motivated to work that high usually have the achievement of work is also high.

Suharto and Cahyono (2005) and Hakim (2006) mentioned that there is one factor that influences Job Performance, which is motivation, where motivation is a condition that moves a person to try to achieve goals or achieve the desired results. Rivai (2004) shows that the stronger work motivation, employee Job Performance will be higher. This means that any increase in employee motivation will provide a very significant increase in improving employee performance in carrying out their work.

Motivation is a mental drive towards individuals or people as group members in responding to an event in the community. Jewel and Marc (1998), motivation refers to the amount of power that generates, directs and sustains effort in certain behaviors. High or low Job Performance is determined by the level of work motivation. This is confirmed by research Devi (2009). In his research, Devi using motivational variables and the results of research that is the motivation effect is significant on employee performance. Because the motivation given by managers are expected to make employees work more enterprising and willing to achieve optimal results, the company's policy to provide motivation is closely related to Job Performance will be achieved. Then his Job Performance will increase. The formulation of the proposed hypothesis is:

H2 : motivation influences Job Performance

Feedback and Job Performance

Spreitzer (quoted by Rahman et al. 2007) based on research conducted by Lawler (1992), concluded that there are two information (feedbacks) that affect employee empowerment. The first information relates to the organization's mission and the second information relates to the Job Performance of the employees themselves. The first information about the mission of the organization. This information helps create employee understanding of company goals and directs employees to act in accordance with existing organizational goals (Conger and Kanugo, 1989; Lawler, 1992 cited by Rahman et al. 2007). The second information, which further affects empowerment, is related to Job Performance. This information actually functions so that employees know about how big their role is to increase the company's success and how well their work is done. In addition, information about Job Performance will also

minimize the sense of uncertainty in employees by providing an evaluation of each job.

Information about the strategy and performance of one's duties is expected to create more meaningful. That is because with information about strategies and Job Performance can help someone realize the vision and mission of the organization and how the task should be carried out properly. Related to the dimension of *self-determination*, that information about Job Performance will provide guidance on how to maintain or improve Job Performance and can strengthen one's understanding of the company's goals. Gist and Mitchell (1992) (quoted by Rahman et al 2007) states that the perception of competence (*Competence*) strengthened by providing information that can improve the understanding of an individual on a task, the complexity of the task and the task environment. Thomas et al (1993) (cited by Rahman et al 2007) state that employees who use Job Performance information will have greater control over problems at the company. This gives employees the feeling as if they have a great influence on the company where they work (*perceived impact*)

Feedback is a response to the message that is sent to the sender (Muhammad, 2001:18). Feedback can improve employee performance (as a resource) better than before. Therefore, there is no deviation from the company's Job Performance. In addition, Job Performance is expected to be able to satisfy the desires of the company's work partners. This is confirmed by research Ariyani (2001). In her research, Ariyani concluded that there was a positive influence between training, incentives and feedback on motivation and Job Performance.

H3 : Feedback influences Job Performance

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a *survey* research method that is a study that takes a sample from a population by relying on the questionnaire as an instrument of data collection. Thus, this research is categorized as *explanatory research*, namely research that explains the causal relationship between research variables through hypothesis testing through the F test and t test (Indriantoro and Supomo, 2002).

Determination of the sample is part of the population that is expected to represent the population as a whole; the population in this study are all employees of BPR ADB and BPR EUJ. Sugiyono (2003:72) argues, "The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population". Regarding the size of the sample must be taken, Mantra in Singarimbun and Efendi (2005:25) suggested that: "The size of the sample that must be taken to obtain representative data some researchers stated that the sample size should not be less than 10% but there are also experts who stated the minimum sample 5% of the elementary number of a population "

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After partial statistical testing (individual) using the t test, then further analysis of the results of the regression analysis are: To find out whether or not the significant influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable is partially, then it is done by t test. T test results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results t-Test

Information	Regression Coefficient	T-value	t-table	Significant
Constants (a)	5,643			
Commitment (X1)	0.073	.481	2,0129	0.633
Motivation (X 2)	.351	2,532	2,0129	0.015
Feedback (X 3)	0.318	1,673	2,0129	.101

Table 1 shows that the Commitment variable (X1) has a t-count of 0.481, which is then compared to t table whose magnitude is 2, 0129. It turned out that t count < t table was obtained (0.481 < 2, 0129). Meanwhile, it is significance, the amount is 0.633, which means

greater than 0, 05. This means that Ho is accepted, and Ha is rejected. The results show that the commitment variable does not have a significant positive effect on the variable Job Performance (Y). Table 4:18 draw motivation variable (X2) has a value t-value amounted to

2,532, which is then compared with t table which magnitude is two, 0129. It turns out that $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ ($2,532 > 2, 0129$) is obtained. Meanwhile, for the significance value owned, the amount is 0.015, which means it is smaller than 0, 05. This means that H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted. The results showed that the Motivation variable had a significant positive effect on the Job Performance variable (Y).

The notions that can be explained according to Table 1 are: Feedback variable (X3) has a t value of 1.673, which is then compared with t table whose magnitude is 2, 0129. It turned out that $t\text{-value} < t \text{ table}$ ($1,673 < 2, 0129$) was obtained.

Meanwhile, for the significance value that is owned, the amount is 0.101, which means it is greater than 0, 05. This means that H_0 is accepted, and H_a is rejected. The results show that the Feedback variable does not have a significant positive effect on the Job Performance variable (Y).

Based on the calculations in appendix 10, it can be seen that the value of the multiple determination coefficient (R^2) is 0.343 (34, 3 %). The magnitude of this value indicates the magnitude of the proportion (percentage) of influence that can be explained by the variable Commitment, Motivation and Feedback together on the magnitude of variation (difficulties) of the dependent variable. Where the dependent variable (Y) can be explained by the three independent variables at 34, 3 %, while the remaining amount ($100\% - 34.3\%$) = 65.7% influenced by other variables outside the research model.

In order to know the magnitude of the contribution of independent variables, namely: Commitment (X1), Motivation (X2) and Feedback (X3) partially on the dependent variable namely Job Performance (Y) and to find out which variables have a dominant influence on Job Performance analysis of the coefficient of partial determination.

Based on the results of the calculation of the regression coefficient analysis, which includes Commitment (X1), Motivation (X2) and Feedback (X3) shows that the variable that gives a dominant influence on Job Performance is the Motivation variable (X2). This can be seen from the partial correlation value of each variable, namely Commitment (X1) of 0.071, Motivation (X2) of 0.350 and Feedback (X3) of 0.239.

Influence of Commitment on Job Performance

The results of this study stated that the Commitment has a significant effect on Job Performance at PT. BPR ADB. While the results of research at PT. BPR EUJ, Commitment has no significant effect on Job Performance. In this case, the higher the commitment the better the Job Performance. In theory, Job Performance is defined as an expression of ability based on knowledge, attitudes, skills and motivation in producing something (Lower in Sari, 2005:3). Work Achievement can be advanced and reach the best level by identifying and analyzing work activities. Commitment is one of the influential factors in order to improve the Performance Works. Commitment can be measured by *Affective commitment, Continuance commitment, and normative commitment*. McNeese-Smith (1996) in Suparman (2007) found that commitment was positively related to employee Job Performance.

The findings of this study are consistent and support the results of research by McNeese-Smith (1996) in Suparman (2007) which shows evidence of a positive relationship between commitment and Job Performance. Based on the description above, the hypothesis stating that commitment has an effect on Job Performance is proven true.

Effect of Motivation on Job Performance

The results of this study stated that motivation has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. BPR EUJ. While the results of research at PT. BPR ADB, Commitment has no significant effect on Job Performance. In this case, the higher the motivation, the better the Job Performance. In theory, motivation can be measured by power motivation, affiliate motivation and competency motivation. In addition, according to Jae (2000) in Suparman (2007) shows that employee motivation is very effective to improve and meet employee job satisfaction where the motivational factors are measured through intrinsic factors (achievement needs and interests) and extrinsic factors (job security, salary and promotion).

Motivation will affect Job Performance. This is because the higher the Motivation, the higher the Job Performance that will be

generated at the company. Morrison (1994) in Suparman (2007) provides an understanding of motivation as one's tendency to involve oneself in activities that lead to the target. If such behavior leads to an object (target market) then the motivation will be obtained target or targets as much as possible so that the implementation of the tasks can be done as well as possible, so that the effectiveness of the work can be achieved. According to Gibson (1997) in Suparman (2007), motivation is a force that drives an employee to cause and direct behavior. Therefore, it can be further concluded that motivation is a series of activity of giving encouragement that is not only to others but also to yourself. So that through this encouragement is expected to be able to act towards the desired goals. Vroom (1964) in Luthan (2005) said the power of motivation is valence and hope. Expectancy theory argues that motivation is determined by the individual's beliefs that relate to, undertakings relations performance (expectancy = expectation), the relationship of work-results (instrumentality = intermediary), and the perception of the importance of various kinds of results of work (valence = valence).

Based on the description above, the hypothesis, which states that motivation influences Job Performance, is proven to be true.

Effect of Feedback on Job Performance

The results of this study stated that motivation has no significant effect on employee Job Performance at PT. BPR EUJ and PT. BPR ADB. In this case, the higher the Feedback the better the Job Performance. In theory, the feedback process is an evaluation process for the development of individuals, usually managers. In this system (Antonioni, 1996), individuals evaluate themselves and receive feedback from other organizational members. This feedback comes from direct superiors and colleagues (*peers*) and from subordinates if the individual is a manager. Even that feedback can come from customers. This system has emerged as an important performance appraisal tool in recent years and, more importantly as a human resource development tool. By comparing the results of one's own assessment and those of others, we can see gaps that can provide useful information for personnel development goals.

The results of this study are consistent and support the research findings of Ariyani (2001). In her research, Ariyani concluded that

there was a positive influence between training, incentives and feedback on motivation and Job Performance. From the description above, the hypothesis stating that feedback influences Job Performance is proven true.

Effect of Commitment, Motivation and Feedback on Job Performance

The results of this study state that commitment, motivation and feedback simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance at PT. BPR EUJ and PT. BPR ADB. In this case, the higher the commitment, motivation and feedback the better the Job Performance. In theory, Job Performance is a manifestation of the work of someone who will determine the development of his career in the future that will come.

According to Hasibuan (2002) Job Performance is a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skill, experience, and sincerity. Lopes in Swasto (1996), argues that Job Performance is actions or implementation of tasks that have been completed by someone within a certain period and can be measured. This relates to the quantity of work that can be completed by individuals within a certain period.

Assessing Job Performance is a difficult job, especially in establishing job criteria. According to Flippo in Sariyathi (2007), Job Performance measurement can be done through assessments (1) work quality, which is related to accuracy, skills, accuracy, and neatness of work implementation; (2) the quantity of work, which is related to the implementation of regular and additional tasks; (3) toughness, which is related to obedience to follow orders, habits to follow regulations, safety, initiative, and timeliness of attendance; and (4) attitude, which shows the extent of responsibility for the implementation of work and how the level of cooperation with friends and superiors in completing work. According to Dharma (1985), Job Performance measurement considers (1) quantity, i.e. the amount of work to be done; (2) quality, that is the quality produced; and (3) timeliness, i.e. compliance with the planned time. According to Sharif (1987), Job Performance measurement is quality (smoothness, cleanliness, accuracy), amount of time (speed), number of types of work (number of expertise), number of types of tools (skills in using various kinds of tools), and knowledge of work

Based on the description above, the hypothesis, which states that commitment, motivation and feedback affect Job Performance, is proven true.

Based on the descriptions that have been disclosed in the discussion, it can be some conclusions in response to the fundamental problems posed in this study influence commitment, motivation and Feedback on Job Performance By RB Award Dharmayuwana Banyuwangi conclusion:

- a) Commitment has a significant positive effect on performance variables with a regression coefficient of 1.806.
- b) Motivation influence positively in not significant to the Job Performance variables with regression coefficient of 0.052.
- c) Feedback affect positively not significant to the variable Job Performance with regression coefficient of 0.077.

In connection with the influence of variables Commitment, Motivation and Feedback on Job Performance at BPR EUJ, conclusions can be obtained:

- a) Commitment has insignificant positive effect on the variable Job Performance with a regression coefficient of 0.073.
- b) Motivation has a significant positive effect on Job Performance variables with a regression coefficient of 0.351.
- c) U Feedback positive effect is not significant to the variable Job Performance with regression coefficient of 0.318.

4. CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the data analysis, the effect of variable commitment, motivation and feedback on Job Performance, it can be concluded that: the BPR ADB, variable commitment, motivation and feedback are simultaneously influenced significantly to the Job Performance variables. One independent variable, namely: partial commitment significantly influence Job Performance. While the other two independent variables, namely: motivation and feedback, have no significant effect on Job Performance. Commitment is the independent variable that has the most influence on Job Performance.

In the BPR EUJ, the variables of commitment, motivation and feedback simultaneously have a significant effect on Job Performance variables. One independent variable is: motivation partially has a significant effect on Job Performance. While the other two independent variables, namely: commitment and feedback have no significant effect on Job Performance. Motivation is the independent variable that has the most influence on Job Performance.

Limitations

Although this research has been done well, there are certain limitations, which cannot be avoided. Based on research that has been done, this research cannot be separated from weaknesses and limitations, namely:

1. This study uses a survey method using a questionnaire in collecting data. So it is possible the respondents who did not answer it seriously and not honest or because of factors bustle in the work, then it is beyond the control researcher.
2. This research uses the object of research in the banking environment, therefore the results of this study cannot be generalized and it is possible to produce different research results if the research is conducted on companies that have different cultural backgrounds.

Suggestions

From the results of the research is presumably the researcher can provide advice, including:

1. BPR ADB seeks to increase commitment as a primary means of improving Job Performance through support for ideas conveyed by employees, responses to employees experiencing problems, and attention to employee welfare and health, because from the research results it is known that commitment makes the most contribution big on Job Performance. Whereas for BPR EUJ it is better to increase work motivation of its employees through training, giving awards for outstanding employees, approaching employees by the leadership and holding special activities to build a kinship between employees and the company. This was obtained from the results of research on BPR EUJ where

motivation is known to provide the greatest contribution to Job Performance.

2. The results of the research it can be used as a source of ideas for the development of research is future that will come. The expansion of research is to add variables independently, such as organizational culture, organizational climate. It in order to provide a general description better and more about the study of Job Performance.

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